

INVESTIGATION ON THE ENERGY ABSORPTION CAPABILITY OF COMPOSITE CRASH-BOX WITH RECYCLABLE THERMOPLASTIC MATERIAL

S. Boria¹, A. Scattina²

¹School of Science and Technology, University of Camerino
9 Madonna delle Carceri, Camerino, Italy

Email: simonetta.boria@unicam.it, web page: <http://www.unicam.it>

²Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, Politecnico di Torino
24 Duca degli Abruzzi, Torino, Italy

Email: alessandro.scattina@polito.it, web page: <http://www.polito.it>

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays the key points in the automotive design are the pollutant emissions and the safety. For these reasons, on one side, in the car design the tendency is to use innovative lightweight materials in order to reduce the weight of the vehicle and consequently the fuel consumption and the gas emissions. On the other side, to reach high level of safety, these materials have to be able to absorb high amount of energy in case of impact. For these reasons, in the last decades, the use of composites as design material for impact attenuators in automotive design is increased significantly. The ever-wider use of composite materials for automotive applications involves the need to predict their behaviour under various load conditions which they are subjected, for example with the use of finite element codes. Moreover, more recently, the strong emphasis on recyclability from the end-of-life vehicle directive seems to affect significantly the choice of materials in the design phase.

In this overview, the use of thermoplastic composite based components for vehicle structure is investigated in this work. In particular a thermoplastic fibres combined with a thermoplastic matrix is considered. An experimental test campaign, in order to define the mechanical properties of this new material is carried out. Starting from the information obtained in the first experimental tests, the energy absorption capacity of impact attenuators made as thin wall tubes of circular cross section is investigated. The crushing sensitivity of these structures to the wall thickness and to the resistant section is studied. The experimental results and the failure mechanisms obtained in the tests are presented and discussed in the paper.

1 INTRODUCTION

Lightweight design has always been an important topic in product planning across several industries [1]. The concept has been important in aviation, but also in wind industries and in automotive where driving dynamics, agility and fuel consumption are the major considerations [1]. Global trend toward CO₂ reduction and resource efficiency have significantly increased the importance of this topic over the last years. While the lightweight share is currently highest in aviation with almost 80 percent, automotive is massively increasing the lightweight share from 30 to 70 percent by 2030. However all lightweight materials offer a significant weight advantage, but come at higher cost (Fig. 1). Aluminum, for example, is 40% lighter than steel, but 30% more expensive. Carbon fiber has the highest weight reduction potential (50% lighter than steel), but by far the highest cost (570% the cost of steel today).

Figure 1: Comparison of cost and weight with different lightweight materials for an automotive fender.

Due to the high cost of potential lightweight solutions and consumers' limited willingness to pay for weight reduction in automotive, the use of costly lightweight materials has so far been limited. The introduction of CO₂ emission targets and correlated penalties, however, has reignited the conversation with an even stronger focus on weight reduction as a lever to minimize fuel consumption [2-4]. The trend of ever-increasing weight for cars has been curtailed in recent years through the increased use of plastics and improved steel alloys [5, 6]. Various lightweight materials are in use, but the particular material used depends on its properties and the requirements of the application. For example, one material may offer superior stiffness while another is more malleable. Focusing the attention on the carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP), it joins together the high resistance to deformation and to both acid and alkaline corrosion. Its potential for helping to meet demands for energy saving and CO₂ reduction in the automotive field has drawn increasing attention of late. Conventional CFRP use thermosetting resin, which hardens when heated during the cure. This material requires several minutes or hours to mold in the desired shape, it is not suitable as a material for mass-produced automobiles. Moreover, the cost of these materials are very high, for this reason they have usually used on high segment or sport cars. Highly stressed load-bearing structures and crash components made in composites are designed to buckle on impact in order to absorb the energy of the impact and consequently to protect the vehicle's occupants in the event of a collision. However, these materials tend to chip into sharp-edged splinters during an impact. It is therefore necessary to find a way for the automotive industry to mass-produce a particularly safe class of lightweight materials that can absorb the energy in a collision without splintering. Moreover, the currently used composites made with a thermoset matrix, brings to components that cannot be recycled at the end of life.

A possible solution to these problems can be the development of a new class of materials designed for large-scale use in vehicle construction, such as composite materials where both the fiber and the matrix are made in thermoplastic. Not only they can be shredded, melted down and reused to produce high quality parts, they have also been found to perform significantly better in crash tests [7, 8]. When reinforced with textile structures they can absorb the energy of a collision through viscoelastic deformation of the matrix material, without splintering. While thermosetting composites involve several stages of processing, thermoplastic ones requires just two steps (press molding and demolding). For these reasons, the thermoplastic composite enables highly efficient production. Moreover, the cost of the thermoplastic matrix material and the cost of its processing are up to 50% lower than the equivalent costs for thermoset structures. Compared with traditional metals, plastics and thermoset composites, the fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites are lighter, tougher, stiffer and more sustainable because they can be easily recycled and repaired. Moreover they can be produced in high volumes with low costs.

In this overview, in this work the use of thermoplastic composite for vehicle structure components is investigated. In particular a plain thermoplastic weave combined with a thermoplastic matrix is considered. An experimental test campaign is carried out, in order to define the mechanical properties of this innovative material under different load conditions. In particular tensile, compression and bending tests have been done in quasi static conditions. The results of these tests and the consequently mechanical properties obtained are presented and discussed. Starting from the information obtained in the first experimental tests, the energy absorption capacity of impact attenuators made of thin walled tubes of circular cross section, in thermoplastic composite is analysed. In particular, the crushing sensitivity of the specimens to the wall thickness and to the resistant section under quasi-static loading and the failure mechanisms, obtained in the different cases examined are presented and discussed.

2 MATERIAL

The material studied in this work is a sealable, co-extruded triple layer polypropylene (PP) tape. It was provided by Lankhorst Pure Composites. It was produced via the patented PURE technology. The PURE tapes are co-extruded and consist of a highly oriented, high strength and high modulus core and a specially formulated skin on both sides for welding the taper together in a compaction process using a hot-press or continuous belt press. The picture below (Fig. 2) shows schematic the processing step of PURE. This process of co-extrusion and tape welding has enormous advantages over conventional sealing processes because of the large sealing windows (130-180°C) without loss of material properties. PURE material has a high stiffness and low density; the combination of these two properties makes PURE an interesting option for automotive products. Moreover PURE material gives good properties with respect to impact resistance showing a “soft” (safer) crash behavior. PURE does not splinter, but fails in a more ductile manner. PURE tapes were used for weaving into thermoformable plain fabric processes, using PP fibers embedded in the same PP matrix, thus achieving a mono material concept which is fully recyclable. Table 1 reports the main mechanical properties for tape and sheet configuration according the PURE technical data sheet.

In the present work the PURE fabrics were then consolidated using 53 layers into a 600x1200 mm sheet. The flat specimens were obtained from this sheet using the waterjet cut Suprema DX 510 of MBR Technology. Such PP material exhibits only minimal water absorption and permeability. For this reason the waterjet cutter seems the best option to obtain the desired tolerance. The production of cylindrical specimens, instead, was done by Von Roll Deutschland GmbH, thanks to its experience with the production of tubes out of PURE.

Figure 2: Schematic processing step of PURE.

PURE tape	Test method	Value	Unit
E-modulus	ISO 527	14	GPa
Tensile strength	ISO 527	500	MPa
Elongation	ISO 527	6	%
Shrinkage at 130°	ASTM D4974	<5.5	%
Sealing range		130-180	°C
PURE sheet	Test method	Value	Unit
Bulk density	ASTM D792	0.78	g/cm ³
Tensile modulus	ISO 527-4	5.5	GPa

Tensile strength	ISO 527-4	200	MPa
Tensile strain to failure	ISO 527-4	9	%
Flexural modulus	ISO 178	4.5-5.5	GPa
Charpy impact (FN)	ISO 179	(N, no break)	kJ/m^2
Charpy impact (EP notched type A)	ISO 179	(P) 140	kJ/m^2
Izod impact (FN)	ISO 180	(N, no break)	kJ/m^2
Izod impact (EP notched type A)	ISO 180	(P) 126	kJ/m^2
Instrumented falling dart impact (23°C) (2.2 mm, clamped, 20 mm striker)	ISO 6603-2	9.51	kN (peak)
Heat deflection temperature (1820 kPa)	ASTM D648	51.46	J (at failure)
Coefficient of thermal expansion (-20°C to 100°C)	ASTM E228	95	°C
Coefficient of thermal conductivity (2.25mm)	EN-ISO 12567-1	23	10^{-6}K^{-1}
Fire behaviour-burning rate (1.6mm)	ISO 3795	0.044	W/m.K
		29	mm/min

Table 1: Mechanical properties for PURE tape and sheet.

3 QUASI-STATIC TESTS FOR MECHANICAL CHARACTERIZATION

Standard coupon tests were performed in tension, compression and three points bending according to ASTM Standards D3039, D3410 and D790, respectively. The tests were conducted in quasi static conditions with a servo-hydraulic Instron 8801 testing machine. The tests were made at the Laboratory of the Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering of the Politecnico di Torino.

3.1 Tensile test

The specimens used for the tensile tests had a rectangular shape with the following dimensions: length 250 mm, width 20 mm with a thickness of 6.9 mm. The tensile tests were conducted in displacement control at three different crosshead speed (0.1, 5 and 100 mm/s) in order to evaluate the sensitivity of the material to the strain rate. The longitudinal strain of the specimens was measured by means of a dynamic extensometer Instron 2620-604 (Fig. 3). The tests were conducted up to the loss of load, consequently, at the highest speed, up to failure (Fig. 4). The specimens after the test are shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 3: The testing equipment.

Figure 4: Specimens at the end of the tensile test, front view on the left, side view on the right.

The results of the tensile tests in terms of force-displacement and stress-strain diagrams are showed in Fig. 5. Fig. 6 shows the most important mechanical parameters as a function of the speed test. The general mechanical properties were calculated, as reported in Table 2. As it is possible to see, the results are influenced by the speed of the test. The elastic modulus and the tensile strength increase with the growth of the test speed, while the strain to failure decrease. Increasing the test speed, as it happens with plastic materials or metals, there is a certain hardening of the material. During the tensile test the first fracture happens on the fibers positioned on the external surface (polymer A on Fig. 2), then there is a sort of delamination and relaxation by the fibers position in the inner part (polymer B in Fig 2). It seems that the specimen, before the test, is subjected to residual stress. Increasing the test velocity it is easier to see the delamination of the specimen.

Figure 5: Force-displacement (on the left) and stress-strain (only for the first linear part, on the right) diagrams for specimens under tensile test.

Figure 6: Young's modulus, tensile strength and tensile strain to failure as a function of the speed test.

Engineering constant		Average value	Standard deviation
ρ	[g/cm ³]	0.78	-
E	[GPa]	3.4	0.10
σ_u	[MPa]	217.8	2.27
ε	[%]	5.9	0.31

Table 2: Mechanical properties for the thermoplastic composite under tension.

3.2 Compression test

The specimens used for the compression test had rectangular shape with the following dimensions: length 150 mm, width 20 mm with a thickness of 6.9 mm. Compression tests were conducted at the crosshead speed of 2 mm/min. The tests were conducted up to loss of load (Fig. 7). The results of the tests in terms of force-displacement and stress-strain diagrams are showed in Fig. 8. The mechanical properties were calculated, as reported in Table 3. In the compression test the drop of the load is due to the delamination of the different layer with a consequently slip of one layer to another one. There is a sort of packing of the fibers. Consequently the thickness of the specimen after the compression is higher than the initial one. In some specimens, it is possible to note a little step in correspondence of the edge of the clamping device. This is due to higher compression stroke, causing a packing of the fiber against the clamping grip.

Figure 7: Specimens at the end of the compression tests, on the left a front view, on the right a side view.

Figure 8: Force-displacement (on the left) and stress-strain (on the right) diagrams for specimens under compression test.

Engineering constant		Average value	Standard deviation
E	[GPa]	5.1	0.21
σ_u	[MPa]	17.5	0.57
ε	[%]	0.52	0.01

Table 3: Mechanical properties for the thermoplastic composite under compression.

3.3 Three points bending test

The specimens, used for the three points bending tests, have the same geometry of that used for compression test. Such tests were conducted at the crosshead speed of 2.85 mm/min, according to what is proposed by the regulation. For the same reason the span between the two support was fixed to 107 mm. The tests were conducted up to loss of load (Fig. 9). The results of the tests, in terms of force-displacement and stress-strain diagrams, are showed in Fig. 10, while the mechanical properties were calculated, as reported in Table 4. As it is possible to see in the picture of the specimen and in the results, the first loss of the load is due to the detachment of the fiber near the central support (polymer A, Fig. 2), where the load is applied. Increasing the stroke it is possible to note a sharp drop of the load; this is due to the delamination of a part of the specimen on one side (in the Polymer B part, see Fig. 2 and Fig. 10). This cause a reduction of the resistance cross section. Subsequently the load is quite constant thanks to the ductile properties of the material.

Figure 9: The testing machine before (on the left) and during (on the right) the three points bending tests.

Figure 10: Specimens at the end of the bending test: front view on the left, top view on the right.

Figure 11: Force-displacement (on the left) and stress-strain (on the right) diagrams for specimens under three points bending test.

Engineering constant		Average value	Standard deviation
E	[GPa]	4.7	0.11
σ_u	[MPa]	76.4	4.18

Table 4: Mechanical properties for the thermoplastic composite under flexure.

4 QUASI-STATIC TESTS FOR ENERGY ABSORPTION CAPABILITY

In order to analyse the energy absorption capability of the material examined, considering a possible use as structural components, static tests on thin-walled cylindrical tubes were carried out. The geometric characteristics of the specimens are summarized in Table 4. The structures differ for the inside diameter D_i , the wall thickness t , while maintaining a constant height of 200 mm. The different specimens were identified by a code defined as D_i-t , as summarized in Table 5.

The specimens were tested with the same equipment and the same conditions described before (Fig. 12). The test speed was set equal to 5 mm/s for a maximum axial crushing of 100 mm.

# Specimen	Code	Inside diameter D_i	Wall thickness t
1	50_2	50	2
2	50_3	50	3
3	50_4	50	4
4	80_2	80	2
5	80_3	80	3
6	80_4	80	4
7	100_2	100	2
8	100_3	100	3
9	100_4	100	4

Table 5: Geometric characteristics of the specimens.

The load-displacement and the energy variation chart, for all the tested specimens, are shown in Fig. 13. Table 6 reports some parameters characterizing the crush resistance under static loading evaluated with the experimental tests. In particular, the values of the average crushing stress, the absorbed energy and the specific energy absorbed (SEA) were calculated.

Such PURE material under axial loading shows a “soft” crash behavior. It does not splinter, but fails in a more ductile manner. Examining in detail the deformation during the crush tests (Fig. 14), the main behavior is a non-regular folding. For the lowest diameter after a certain package of the material (around 50 mm of stroke) the deformation mechanism change from folding to bending, consequently the process became instable. This phenomenon is present in a different way increasing the diameter. In particular with the highest wall thickness in some cases the deformation mechanism change from folding to diamond [9-11]. The most regular behavior in terms of energy absorption was obtained with the intermediate diameter and thickness.

Figure 12: Specimen under quasi-static compression before (on the left) and after (on the right) the test.

Figure 13: Load (on the right) and crushing stress (on the left) versus displacement for all tested tubes.

# Specimen	Code	Average crushing stress [MPa]	Absorbed energy [kJ]	SEA [kJ/kg]
1	50_2	13.64	0.45	17.52
2	50_3	18.49	0.93	23.77
3	50_4	12.84	0.88	16.84
4	80_2	9.56	0.49	12.28
5	80_3	11.51	0.95	15.82
6	80_4	6.34	0.71	8.69
7	100_2	9.34	0.91	18.48
8	100_3	15.05	1.52	20.42
9	100_4	13.82	1.88	18.69

Table 6: Static results for the tested specimens.

Figure 14: Specimens at the end of the compression test. From top to down the diameter increases, from left to right the thickness increases.

Figure 15 shows how the average crushing stress and specific energy absorption vary with the thickness/inner diameter ratio (t/D_i). Also if the data are quite scattered, it is clear that increasing the wall thickness or decreasing the inside diameter the values increase almost linearly. Such aspect was also observed for thin-walled CFRP composite structures under axial loading [12].

Figure 15: Average crushing stress and SEA varying the ratio t/D_i .

5 CONCLUSIONS

The paper describes the experimental campaign conducted on a new thermoplastic composite, where both the fibres and the matrix are made with thermoplastic. The experimental tests were made in order to characterize the material from the mechanical point of view and to verify its ability to absorb energy when used to make thin-walled cylindrical tubes. Tensile, compression and three points bending tests were conducted, under quasi-static conditions, according to ASTM Standard. Moreover, axial crushing experimental tests on simple cylindrical structures were done. In this configuration the sensibility of the wall thickness and of the dimension of the tubes was investigated.

As regards the failure mechanisms of such thermoplastic structures, it is possible to note crushing processes between conventional and composite materials. As for metallic structures under axial loading, it is possible to observe a sequence of small plastic hinges according to the concertina or diamond deformation modes, but differently from them the force-shortening characteristic does not present a clear set of higher and lower peaks. An almost constant crushing strength throughout the deformation process it is evident, as happens for composite structures, although this does not involve a brittle failure. For some specimens, after a certain stroke, it is possible to observe a loss of load capacity due to a change in deformation type, that pass from folding to bending. Therefore the crushing behaviour of such new material is quite interesting because, choosing in right way the combination of the thickness and the diameter of the tube, it is possible to obtain a regular folding behaviour with a consequently high and regular energy absorption. For these reasons this material shows good opportunity to be used as lightweight material in automotive applications.

Finally both the SEA and the average stress values have been calculated for each test. Analysis of the results clearly puts in evidence that to improve the energy absorption capacity of the component it is useful to increase the thickness of the laminate and to decrease the inside diameter. To avoid no regular deformation and instable behaviour the value of the diameter should be carefully defined. Therefore, between the different solutions examined it seems reasonable to define as the best solution the intermediate condition, that is using a tube with 80 mm in diameter and 3 mm thick. For this solution, the trend of the load curve during crushing is very regular without oscillations, such as an ideal energy absorber.

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